

A functional network model of the metastasis suppressor RKIP and its regulators in breast cancer cells

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Outline

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Introduction

STAGES OF BREAST CANCER

Overview of Metastatic Cascade

Metastasis suppressor genes and steps in the metastatic cascade in human cancer

[Smith and Theodorescu, 2009]

Timeline | Key advances in the metastasis suppressor field

[Smith and Theodorescu, 2009]

Functions and reported targeting strategies of Metastasis suppressor genes

Symbol	Alias(es)	Function(s)	Potential targeting strategy
BMP4	BMP2B	Soluble cytokine	Direct therapeutic administration of suppressor protein*
BRMS1	None	Chromatin and transcriptional regulation; regulation of gap junctions	None published at present
CTGF	CCN2, IGFBP8	Soluble cytokine	None published at present
DLC1	ARHGAP7	Regulation of RhoGTPase signalling	Re-induction of endogenous gene through HDAC inhibition ⁶⁹
KAI1	CD82, kangai 1	Inhibition of EGFR signaling; induction of senescence through interaction with DARC	Therapeutic re-induction of endogenous gene by plant extracts ⁶⁰ ; viral ⁶¹ and non-viral ⁶¹ gene therapy
KISS1	KiSS-1, metastin	Soluble ligand for G-protein-coupled receptor	Direct therapeutic administration of suppressor protein ⁶¹ ; possibly small molecule mimetics ⁶⁴
MKK4	MAP2K4	Signal transduction	Antibody-mediated activation pathway upstream of MKK4 (REF. 122)
NDRG1	CAP43, DRG1, RTP	Unknown	Induced by iron chelators ¹²³ , p53 (REF. 124) and PTEN expression ¹²⁵
NM23	NME1, NM23-H1	Histidine kinase activity to KSR1, decreasing Ras signalling; regulation of downstream gene expression	Re-induction of endogenous gene ^{42,47,48} ; viral gene therapy ⁴⁹ ; inhibition of downstream genes ⁴⁰
RHOGD12	ARHGDI2, LyGDI, GDID4	Regulation of Rho family member activation; regulation of downstream gene expression	Inhibition of downstream genes ⁶⁵
RKIP	PEBP1	Binds to and inhibits Raf kinase activity and downstream signalling	Epigenetic re-induction of endogenous gene ⁶⁷

[Smith and Theodorescu, 2009]

Materials and Methods

- Protein-protein interactions (STRINGDB), literature search and biological expression language (BEL)
- Knockdown of metastasis suppressors and transcription factors
- Pharmacological perturbations of breast cancer cell lines
- Network Perturbation Amplitude (NPA)
- Measures of consistency
- Software environment and reproducibility

Metastasis suppressor genes (MSG)

[Marino et al., 2014]

- **Cell-cell adhesion:** CD44, CD82, CDH11, CDH2, CDH1 & GSN
- **Scaffolding:** AKAP12
- **MAPK:** MAP2K6, MAP2K4, MAP2K7 & MAPK14
- **Transcription:** NME1 & BRMS1
- **GTP-binding:** ARGHDIB & DRG1
- **Other:** RRM1 & PEBP1

Transcription factors targeting metastasis suppressor genes in MCF7 [Feng et al., 2019]

TF	Name	Dataset ID	Ref.
ESR1	Estrogen receptor 1	GSE10061	[Yau and Benz, 2008]
FOS	Fos Proto-Oncogene AP-1 Transcription Factor Subunit	GSE36586	[Dahlman-Wright et al., 2012]
FOXM1	Forkhead Box M1	GSE55204	[Bergamaschi et al., 2014]
GATA3	GATA Binding Protein 3	GSE39623	[Theodorou et al., 2013]
HIF1A	Hypoxia Inducible Factor 1 Subunit Alpha	GSE3188	[Elvidge et al., 2006]
NR5A2	Nuclear Receptor Subfamily 5 Group A Member 2	GSE47803	[Lai et al., 2013]
POLR3A	RNA Polymerase III Subunit A	GSE42239	[Lee et al., 2015]
RARA	Retinoic Acid Receptor Alpha	GSE26298	[Salazar et al., 2011]
SPDEF	SAM Pointed Domain Containing ETS Transcription Factor	GSE40985	[Buchwalter et al., 2013]
TFAP2C	Transcription Factor AP-2 Gamma	GSE26740	[Tan et al., 2011]
YBX1	Y-Box Binding Protein 1	GSE28433	[Lasham et al., 2012]
ZFX	Zinc Finger Protein X-Linked	ENCSR005AHI	[Dunham et al., 2012]

Drug perturbations in MCF7 cell line

[Koleti et al., 2018]

The cell is the source of ATP in the luciferase reaction, so the luminescence produced is proportional to the number of viable cells.

CellTiter-Glo® Assay is lytic.

VIABLE CELL

Building a network of the metastasis suppressors and their regulators

Identifying protein-protein interaction (PPI) based on STRING database

The image shows the homepage of the STRING database. At the top, there is a dark navigation bar with 'Version: 11.5' on the left and 'LOGIN', 'REGISTER', and 'SURVEY' on the right. Below this is a light-colored header with the STRING logo on the left and 'Search', 'Download', 'Help', and 'My Data' on the right. The main content area has a blue background with a laptop image. It features the text 'Welcome to STRING', 'Protein-Protein Interaction Networks', and 'Functional Enrichment Analysis'. A statistics section displays three columns: 'ORGANISMS' with '14094', 'PROTEINS' with '67.6 mio', and 'INTERACTIONS' with '>20 bln'. A 'SEARCH' button is centered at the bottom.

Version: 11.5

LOGIN REGISTER SURVEY

STRING

Search Download Help My Data

Welcome to STRING

Protein-Protein Interaction Networks
Functional Enrichment Analysis

ORGANISMS		PROTEINS		INTERACTIONS
14094		67.6 mio		>20 bln

SEARCH

Metastasis suppressor proteins and their regulators on STRINGDB

Surveying literature search to establish causal relations between entities

Converting possible interactions of metastasis suppressors to Biological expression language (BEL)

TEXTMINING

Relevant publications mentioning your query species (Homo sapiens):

<p>PMID 22717374 The role of WT1 in breast cancer: clinical implications, biological effects and molecular mechanism.</p> <p>Zhang Y, Yan HT, Yang ZC, Li YL, Yan XN, Cheng J, Zhang Y, Qi XY <i>Int J Clin Oncol.</i> 19(5):1454-1460 2013.</p> <p>Abstract: Although Wilms' tumor gene 1 (WT1) was first cloned and identified as a tumor suppressor gene in nephroblastoma, subsequent studies have demonstrated that it can also play an oncogenic role in leukemia and various solid tumors. WT1 exerts biological functions with high tissue- and cell-specificity. This article reviews the relationship between WT1 and breast cancer from two aspects: (1) clinical application of WT1, including the relationship between expression of WT1 and prognosis of breast cancer patients; and its effectiveness as a target for comprehensive therapy of breast cancer; (2) the biological effects and molecular mechanisms of WT1 in the development and progression of breast cancer, including proliferation, apoptosis, invasion, and metastasis of breast cancer cells.</p> <p>Excerpts from full text: ... patients. We found that high WT1 mRNA expression was associated with high histological grade, estrogen receptor (ER) (ER) (ER) negative status, basal-like subtype, and ERBB2 (erbB2 receptor [L1]) (ErbB-2/HER2) (HER2) (HER2) did not affect p21 expression, but promoted EMT, which was demonstrated by membrane E-cadherin (E-cadherin) (E-cadherin) translocation into the nucleus, and cells developing mesenchymal cell-like ...</p>	<p>PubMed</p>
<p>PMID 22160087 Vasculogenic mimicry in carcinogenesis and clinical application.</p> <p>Luo Q, Wang J, Zhao W, Peng Z, Liu X, Li R, Zhang H, Shan R, Zhang C, Guan C <i>J Hematol Oncol.</i> 13(7):14 2010.</p> <p>Abstract: Distinct from classical tumor angiogenesis, vasculogenic mimicry (VM) provides a blood supply for tumor cells independent of endothelial cells. VM has two distinct types, namely tubular type and patterned matrix type. VM is associated with high tumor grade, tumor progression, invasion, metastasis, and poor prognosis in patients with malignant tumors. Herein, we discuss the recent studies on the role of VM in tumor progression and the diverse mechanisms and signaling pathways that regulate VM in tumors. Furthermore, we also summarize the latest findings of non-coding RNAs such as miRNAs and lncRNAs in VM formation. In addition, we review application of molecular imaging technologies in detection of VM in malignant tumors. Increasing evidence suggests that VM is significantly associated with poor overall survival in patients with malignant tumors and could be a potential therapeutic target.</p> <p>Excerpts from full text: ... breast cancer (TNBC) corresponds to the basal-like subtype of breast cancer that is negative for estrogen receptor (ER) (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor 1 (HER1) (HER1) by specific procedures, including induction of expression of cell adhesion molecules (such as E-cadherin (E-cadherin) (E-cadherin)) and some upregulated proteins (such as VC-cadherin-biomarker of VM) ...</p>	<p>PubMed</p>
<p>PMID 22193204 CDK4/6 inhibition blocks cancer metastasis through a USP51-ZEB1-dependent deubiquitination mechanism.</p> <p>Zhang Z, Li Q, Fan Q, Wang Q, Wang Z, Wang W, Zhang Q, Wang H, Sun W, Sun R, Wang Z <i>Signal Transduct Target Ther.</i> 5:25 2016.</p> <p>PMID 22992005 Estrogen receptor ...</p>	<p>PubMed</p>
<p>PMID 23292005 Herbal Active Ingredients: An Emerging Potential for the Prevention and Treatment of Papillary Thyroid Carcinomas.</p> <p>Peng Y, Chen Q, Yu HF, Zhang HX, Zhang YS, Zhang SC, Wang JF, Yu GH <i>Biomol Res Int.</i> 2012;13(4):51 2012.</p> <p>PMID 22492205 A novel small molecule STAT3 inhibitor SLS-1216 suppresses proliferation and tumor growth in triple-negative breast cancer cells through epigenetic induction.</p> <p>Wei DC, Ryan MS, Lee J, Han TT, Jiang HJ, Jiang K, Chung SJ, Lee J, Sha W, Lee DK <i>Modern Pharmacol.</i> 178:1-14 2012.</p>	<p>PubMed</p>

Protein-protein interactions (STRING)

MSG + TF
Literature survey

Possible causal links (BEL)

Biological expression language (BEL)

What is BEL?

BEL is a language for representing scientific findings in the life sciences in a computable form. BEL is designed to represent scientific findings by capturing causal and correlative relationships in context, where context can include information about the biological and experimental system in which the relationships were observed, the supporting publications cited and the process of curation. [BEL.bio](#)

Why BEL?

Open standard for communication and knowledge storage.

Example of a BEL statement

“ER α (ESR1) is bound to the E-cadherin (CDH1) promoter in both the presence and the complete absence of estrogen. Transfection of ER α , in the absence of ligands, was sufficient to restore E-cadherin transcription.” (*Pmid:19383788*)

(Coding to BEL)
↓

Examples of Interactions of metastasis suppressor genes and their transcription factor

Subject	Object	Ref.	Interaction
MAPK14	FOS	[Janknecht and Hunter, 1997]	act(p(HGNC:6876!MAPK14), ma(kin)) increases p(HGNC:3796!FOS)
MAP2K4	FOS	[Xue et al., 2018]	p(HGNC:6844!MAP2K4) increases p(HGNC:3796!FOS)
MAPK14	GATA3	[Wan, 2014]	p(HGNC:6876!MAPK14) increases act(p(HGNC:4172!GATA3))
RUNX2	HIF1A	[Lee et al., 2012]	p(HGNC:10472!RUNX2) increases act(p(HGNC:4910!HIF1A))
PEBP1	MAP2K6	[Lai et al., 2017]	p(HGNC:8630!PEBP1) increases act(p(HGNC:6846!MAP2K6))
PEBP1	MAP2K3	[Lai et al., 2017]	p(HGNC:8630!PEBP1) increases act(p(HGNC:6843!MAP2K3))
MAPK14	RUNX2	[Hutchison, 2013]	p(HGNC:6876!MAPK14) increases r(HGNC:10472!RUNX2)
NME1	AKAP12	[McCorkle et al., 2014]	r(HGNC:7849!NME1) increases r(HGNC:370!AKAP12)
NME1	PEBP1	[Berger et al., 2005]	r(HGNC:7849!NME1) increases r(HGNC:8630!PEBP1)
PEBP1	MAPK14	[Lai et al., 2017]	p(HGNC:8630!PEBP1) increases act(p(HGNC:6876!MAPK14))
TNFSF10	CASP8	[Mizamtsidi et al., 2018]	p(HGNC:11925!TNFSF10) increases p(HGNC:1509!CASP8)

Fold-change between control and knockdown of metastasis suppressors and transcription factors

Resolving conflicts between possible interactions and fold-changes

- No evidence to the contrary → Keep
- Significant change in the opposite direction → Remove
- Positive significant effects of the knockdown of one node on others as an interaction between the mRNA → Add

	Conflicts		
	Possible Interaction	Observed Fold-change	Consensus
E1	↑	↑	✓
E2	↑		✗ Remove if weak evidence
E3		↓	✓ Add if big effect size

Network of interactions among metastasis suppressors and regulators

The agreement between expected and observed direction of change in the subnetworks and paths.

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad x = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } u.e = x' \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad u = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } u \text{ is activated} \\ -1, & \text{if } u \text{ is repressed} \end{cases}$$

- Where x is the observed and x' is the expected effect on the nodes of the *subnetwork* downstream from u and connected to it by the edges e (**concordance**).
- Where x is the observed and x' is the expected effect on the nodes in a *path* connected by edges e and u is considered moving down the path (**coherence**).

Concordance of expectation and observations in the subnetworks of the metastasis network

$$\kappa = (\text{observed agreement} - \text{expected agreement}) / (1 - \text{expected agreement})$$

Coherence of expectations and observations in the paths to RKIP.

$$\kappa = (\text{observed agreement} - \text{expected agreement}) / (1 - \text{expected agreement})$$

Constructing a model of PEBP1 and its interaction with other metastasis suppressors

A

B

Drug profiles on the nodes of interest

Validating the functional model of RKIP interactions with other metastasis suppressors and regulators

- **Goal:** Testing **gene expression** of related proteins under drug treatments.
- **Cell line:** MCF7- Breast cancer cell
- **Drugs:**
 - ▶ **Activators:** Epirubicin, Vorinostat, Methotrexate
 - ▶ **Repressors:** Cisplatin, Imatinib, Sorafenib
- **Assay:** RT-PCR
- **Target genes:** RKIP, RELA, SNAI, ESR1, NME1

Activation and repression of PEBP1/RKIP and its regulatory pathways.

Summary

- We used text mining datasets and a manual literature search to extract evidence for *possible* interactions between several metastasis suppressors and their regulators.
- We then used the knockdown dataset to filter these interactions in the *context* of the breast cancer cell line MCF7.
- The resulting interactions were coded in the biological expression language (BEL) to build a functional metastasis *model*.
- A reverse causal reasoning approach was used to test and *prioritize* these interactions and extract pathways that are most consistent with drug treatments that inhibit cell growth.
- We suggested that the metastasis suppressor RKIP is on the receiving end of two key regulatory *pathways*. One involves P65 (RELA) and SNAI1, which were previously reported to inhibit RKIP, and the other involves the estrogen receptor (ESR1), which induces RKIP through the kinase NME1.

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